

**WOMEN EMPOWERMENT AND FREEDOM STRUGGLE: A STUDY ON
SARALA DEVI AND RAMA DEVI IN ODISHA**

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ABSTRACT

Mahatma Gandhi once said “As long as women of India do not take part in public life, there can be no salvation for the country. As long as women do not come to public life and purify, we are not likely to attain Swaraj, even if we did, it would have no use for that kind of Swaraj to which women have not made their full contribution”. An attempt has been made in the present paper to provide information about freedom movement and role of women in the freedom struggle of Odisha.

Key words: - Empowerment, Freedom Struggle, women, Odisha.

Introduction:-

In the freedom struggle of India, the Gandhian era witnessed a remarkable event in the history of India. The participation of masses in general and women in particular in the freedom struggle has created a golden page in the annals of history. Before freedom movement in India, in the revolt of 1857, Rani Laxmibai had fought bravely against the British administration in India, although it was to oust British from her territory not for India. But it was during the Gandhian period that the whole masses of India as well as women actively participated in the freedom movement. With the clarion call of Mahatma Gandhi, the women who were confined to the four walls of the house, came out and took active part in the national movement (Das, 2015). Once Gandhiji said to Mridula Sarabhai, a Valliant fighter for his causes of women and freedom, “I have brought the Indian women out of the

kitchen, it is up to you (the women activists) to see that they do not go back (Chandra, 2008).” In this context of national movement, the contribution of Odisha women cannot be ignored. The sacrifice and valour of Odia women will always be remembered in the heart of the people and also recorded by golden letter in History. The participation of Odisha women not only created history but also signified the empowerment of women in Odisha during Gandhian era.

The Women Freedom Fighters of Odisha

In the freedom struggle of India, the famous women of Odisha who played a very important role were *Rama Devi, Sarala Devi, Malati Devi* etc. (Das,1957).

Participation from Undivided Balasore

The women freedom fighter like *Kokila Devi, Nirmala Devi, Janhabi Devi, Kshetramani Devi, Subhadra Mahtab, Sulochana Devi, Purubai, Kundalata Dev, Hemalata Devi, Gauri Devi, Krushnapriya Devi, Bishnupriya Devi* etc. were participated From the undivided Balasore district (Pradhan,2006).

Undivided Cuttack District

From undivided Cuttack district the women who had participated in the freedom struggle were *Kuntala Kumari Sabat, Rama Devi, Sarala Devi, Malati Devi, Kshetramani Devi, Kiranbala Sengupta, Priyambada Devi, Mangala Sengupta, Sashibala Kanungo, Sakuntala Devi, Adharamani Devi, Kiranlekha Mohanty, Ratnamali Jena, Bimala Dutta, Haramani Kanungo* etc had participated (Das, 2015).

Undivided Ganjam District

The women like *Sobhabati Panda, Kishorimani Devi, Kundalata Devi, Champa Devi, Baralakshmi Devi, Hemalata Samanta, Suryama, Apurba Devi, P. Tamma, A. Laxmi Bai,*

T. Arahalu, T.V. Narayani, Sitadevi Khadanga, Malati Panda, Haramani Bisoi, Rasamani *Devi* have participated from undivided Ganjam district (Das, 2015).

Undivided Koraput District

From undivided Koraput district, the women who have have contributed for the sake of the nation were Chitrabhanu *Devi*, Koyarani Banqara *Devi*, Budwal *Devi*, Khara Parbati (Das, 2015).

Participation from Undivided Puri District

From undivided Puri district Saraswati *Devi*, Sunarnan, *Devi*, Radhamani *Devi*, Dhanamani *Devi*, Gunamanjari *Devi*, Nishamani *Devi*, Bimala *Devi* etc had participated. Labanya *Devi*, the wife of advocate Loknath Bahadur of Puri founded a Women's Association at Puri called Mahila Bandhu Samiti (Samal, 1989) and also contributed a lot in the freedom movement in India.

Participation from Undivided Sambalpur District

From undivided Sambalpur district, the women who took part in the freedom struggle of Odisha were Jambhubati *Devi*, Pravabati *Devi*, Parbati Giri, Haramani *Devi* and Rukmini *Devi* etc. (Das, 2015). Besides these women, there were also many common women of Odisha who have contributed a lot for the freedom struggle of India, which history has not remembered. In the least, an acknowledgement for their participation and contribution to the freedom struggle of India should be made.

SARALA DEVI

Among the women of Odisha, Sarala *Devi* played a heroic role and occupied an important place in the history of India. On 9th August 1904 at village Narilo near Balikuda of Jagatsinghpur, the then undivided district of Cuttack, Sarala *Devi* was born in a well to do

Zamindar family. She was adopted as a daughter by her paternal uncle Mr Bala mukunda Kanungo, a renowned Dy. Collector. She was inspired from her childhood to become a poet a leader and a social worker (Kanungo, 2014). She was the sister of Mr. Nityananda Kanungo, niece of Mr. Raj Kishore Dash and cousin of Smt. Rama Devi. Most of her family members were moderate in attitude and against the traditional orthodoxical ideas (Jena, 2014).

Sarala Devi felt that the male dominated society curtailed the rights of women whose duties were only to rear the children and maintain the house like a domestic servant. Child marriage, polygamy, sati, dowry system degraded the status of women. So, by hearing Gandhiji motivation for women to join the national stream speaking about the evils of Sati, child marriage, widowhood, she inspired and joined hand with Gandhi to upgrade the status of women by spreading the message to reform the social evils (Jena, 2014). She joined in the ‘Mahila Samaj’“Sponsored by Smt. Lavanyabati Devi which organization encouraged the women fold of Odisha to join in the Freedom Movement (Kanungo, 2014).

SARALA DEVI

Source: - www.wikipedia.org.in

During 1920, Sarala Devi was inspired by Gandhianism concept and the role of Utkal Sammilani for amalgamation of odia people under the leadership of Madhusudan das and Gopabandhu das (Jena, 2014).

SARALA DEVI AS A FREEDOM FIGHTER:-

Sarala Devi with husband Bhagirathi Mohapatra attended the 35th Indian national congress Nagpur session in 1920. In 1921 when Gandhiji came to Cuttack and addressed the women at Vinodvihari, she attended the meeting and inspired by the principle of non-violence. The speech of Gandhiji was translated from Hindi to Odia by Sarala Devi. She donated all her jewellery to Tilak Swaraj fund and promised not to wear jewellery during her life time. During non-cooperation movement, she played a vital role. She collected fund for Tilak Swaraj fund and spread the message of non-cooperation in every nook and corner of Odisha. (Chand and Tripathy, 2019).

The civil disobedience movement had a lot of impact on Odisha. Under the influence of dandi march started by Gandhi, Gopabandhu Chaudhary and Sarala Devi took active part in salt styagraha at Inchudi and Huma. At Berhampur she started an Ashram known as Udjogi Ashram and made it battle ground. But she was imprisoned by madras govt, as Ganjam was under madras presidency. After released, she formed a Nikhila Utkal Parisada which included the women of various walk of life. She started to perform several road drama to educate women socially and physically. In 1933 along with Nabakrishna Choudhury Sarala Devi attended a huge peasant meeting at Anakhia and encouraged peasant movement (Kanungo, 2014).

In the later part of her life she was engaged with socialism and became an active member in the Utkal Congress Socialist Party .the Active member of this party were Nabakrishna Choudhury, MalatiChoudhury, Bhagabati Panigrahi were activemembers. She

took all initiative to uplift peasant from the state of poverty. When Mahatma Gandhi came to Odisha in 1933 to organize harijana sevaka Sangha she took active part and visited village to village for the upliftment of Harijana and eradication of untouchability (Kanungo, 2014).

Odisha become a separate province in 1936. Sarala Devi became MLA from 1936-41. She was the first odia women to become a member of legislative assembly. During her tenure the bill for establishing “Utkal University” was passed (Kanungo, 2014).

SARALA DEVI AS A WRITER:-

Sarala Devi was not only a freedom fighter social activist but also a writer. She edited two magazine Sabita and Utkalika in 1923 and 1939 respectively. among her famous writing mentioned may be made of Utkalare Nari Samasya, Narira Dabi, Bharatiya Mahila Prasanga, Bira ramani, Purusa jibanare Narira Prabhaba,, Biswa Biplabini, Narira Pratistha and Narira Arthika Swadhinata etc. when press act decided to burn all newspaper, magazine in the commissioner office of Cuttack, Sarala Devi who was a legislator decided to keep all these in Utkala Sahitya Samaj. This was really a historical work of Sarala Devi. She treated both male and female equally. Because she felt that if the women are not treated equally with man than the growth and development of the country is not possible. She was the first lady who by disregarding the then purdah system joined freedom struggle (Chand and Tripathy, 2019).

Sarala Devi was First Woman of Orissa to: -

1. Join the Non-cooperation Movement
2. Wear Khadi.
3. Deliver speech in INC, Karachi session.

4. Represent in Nehru's Planning Commission.
5. Be a member of Senate Board of Utkal University.
6. Join the educational committee constituted by Dr. Radhakrishnan.
7. Be prisoner of Orissa by breaking salt law.
8. Be member of All India Congress Committee.
9. Be elected twice to standing committee of All India Women Conference.
10. Be awarded twice by Orissa Sahitya Academy.
11. Be elected as Woman Legislator of Orissa Legislative Assembly
12. Be act as a temporary speaker of Orissa Legislative Assembly
13. Be the Director of Indian Women Bank
14. Be the Vice President of Utkal Sahitya Samaj
15. Be the President of Women Development Cooperative Society
16. Be create a political consciousness among Oriya Women through her writing (Jena, 2014).

She was also the first lady to create feminist consciousness among the women of Odisha. This great lady breathed her last on 4 October, 1986. Her contribution to Odisha is unparalleled till date.

RAMADEVI

Another dominating figure of Odisha who create a remarkable position in empowering women in the freedom struggle of Odisha was Rama Devi. On 3rd December 1899 she was born to Gopal Ballav Das and Basanta Kumari Devi at Satyabhamapur of

Cuttack district. During her childhood, she was attracted by her uncle's (Madhusudan Das) spirit of nationalism and Sri Aurobindo's philosophy. She married Gopobandhu Choudhury, a Deputy Magistrate. In 1921, Gopobandhu Choudhury left service to join the freedom movement (Ghadai, 2011).

RAMA DEVI

Source: - www.womenodisha.in

It was on 23 March 1921, a meeting of forty women was held inside the Binod Vihari Temple at Cuttack in which Mahatma Gandhi addressed. Rama Devi attended the meeting and inspired by Gandhi's non-violent programmes. She decided to follow the foot-steps of Gandhiji and his ideals and made it the motto of her life. Gandhiji non-violent programmes made a dramatic change in the static life of Oriya women. It was the first occasion when a great political leader Gandhi addressed the women in a separate meeting and it was also first time that Odia women attended a public meeting (Ghadai, 2011).

Rama Devi along with ladies of similar faculty like Hiramani Devi, Sarala Devi & Padmabati Devi attended the Gaya session of Indian National Congress in 1922. In December 1928, she also attended the Calcutta session of I.N. C along with Sarala Devi, Sarojini Choudhury, Janhavi Devi, Kokila Devi and Rasamani Devi. In 1928 she moved to Alka Ashrama, Jagatsingpur and devoted herself to the constructive work of Gandhiji (Ghadai, 2011).

In 1930 the historic salt Satyagraha spread different part of the country. It inspired the women of Odisha who came out the four wall of house and joined the movement. When At in chudi the salt Satyagraha was started, Rama Devi accompanied by Malati Devi, Annapurna Devi, Kiran Bala Sen reached the Satyagraha camp at Balasore and violated the salt law. when Malti devi and Pandit Lingaraj Mishra were arrested , Ramadevi become the director and continued the movement. Under her leadership hundereds of women marched to srijanga in Balasore under her leadership. The Rani Bhagyabati Patamahadei of Kujanga joined the salt Satyagraha which drew special attention. Rama Devi along with Rani Bhagyabati Patamahadei and many other womwn volunteers prepared contraband salt at Kaliapata. In the first phase of the movement six ladies including Rama Devi were arrested. after released from jail she was welcomed by the people. Rama Devi's inspiring speech in all India women conference which was held at Balasore in 1931 created a lot of enthusiasm among the women of Odisha (Chand and Tripathy, 2019).

In 1934 Rama Devi along with her husband left for Bari and being inspired by Gandhiji built a thatched house there named 'Sebaghar'. Both Rama Devi and Gopabandhu chaudhury and workers of Sebaghar devoted themselves to social and economic uplift of the villagers by the constructive programmes like promotion of Khadi, anti-touchability

campaign, national language, women's awakening, prohibition, basic education, adult education, dairy, agriculture, tanning and distribution of medicine (Ghadai, 2011). At the time of Gandhi Harijana padayatra Rama devi organisining ability, leadership ans sincerity inspired the national leader of Odisha. She was one of the chief organiser of the first all India Gandhi Seva Sangha Conference which was held in Beraboi of Delang in the district of Puri. For successful organisation of the conference, Gandhiji praised both Rama Devi and Gopabandhu Choudhury (Chand and Tripathy, 2019).

In august 1942 the quit India movement was lunched. In this movement Rama Devi was arrested and for her participation in the movement she was imprisoned for two years. Even after independence she continued her social work by establishing Kasturba Gandhi Rashtriya Smarak Trust. In the tribal areas of Koraput she established health home for the leprosy patients and their children. She also joined the Sarvadoya Movement started by Binoba Bhave (Chand and Tripathy, 2019).

In 29 April 1958, Gopabandhu Choudhury, the husband of Rama Devi died. Despite of this she continued her humanitarian work. She became the chairperson of the Odisha Relief Committee in 1966. Under her leadership Acharya Harihara Memorial trust was formed in 1977. In Cuttack a cancer detection was established. For her selfless service to women and children, she won the Jamunalal Bajaj Award in 1981. She was awarded the highest D.Litt. Degree by Utkal University for her selfless service in 1984. To spend the amount of one lakh rupees received from Jamunalal Bajaj Award for the welfare of women and children, she formed Ramadlyevi and Gopabandhu Chaudhry trust. This great lady breathed her last on 22 July 1985 (Chand and Tripathy, 2019).

Rama Devi is quite commonly referred to as Maa Rama Devi in every house of Odisha. She is rightly called as the Mother Teresa of Odisha. She was a great Humanist who

sacrificed a luxurious life for freedom struggle and Social service. Her autobiography Jibana Pathe regarded as a source of inspiration for the women of Odisha (Chand and Tripathy, 2019).

Conclusion:-

So it may be concluded that as a women both Sarala Devi and Rama Devi broke the barriers of four walls and joined the freedom struggle during Gandhian Era. They came to the social fore front and engaged themselves in freedom movement and other humanitarian activities. They sacrificed their whole life for the cause of nation. Through their work and speech they inspired the women of Odisha as a lot. So that a huge number of women participated in the freedom struggle in India as well as Odisha. So not only they were a great freedom fighter, writer and social activist but also a beacon of women empowerment in Odisha. Their contribution to Odisha is immense and unparalleled till date.

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